

Reactions of arylhydrazones of dehydro-L-ascorbic acid and of D-arabino-2,3-diulosono-1,4-lactone

M. A. El-Sekily* and S. H. Mancy^a

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Alexandria, Ibrahimia, P.O. Box 426, 21321 Alexandria, Egypt

E-mail : prof_dr_m_a_elsekily@yahoo.com

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Education, University of Alexandria, Egypt

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Abstract : Reaction of D-arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone with *p*-chlorophenylhydrazine gave the bishydrazone 2 characterized as its acetate 3 and rearranged by treatment with hydrazine hydrate, followed by acidification to pyrazolinedione 5 characterized also by its acetate 6. Cupric chloride oxidation of the bis(*p*-bromophenylhydrazone) 4, gave the 3,6-anhydro derivative 7 which afforded the di-*O*-acetyl derivative 8. *p*-Toluenesulfonation of 3,6-anhydro-2-oxo-3-phenylazo-D-glucoheptono-1,4-lactone-2-phenylhydrazone (9), afforded the monotosyl derivative 10. Compound 1 reacted with acetylphenylhydrazine giving the mono (phenylhydrazone) 11 which was converted into an olefinic derivative 13 upon acetylation. L-Threo-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(*p*-chlorophenylhydrazone) 14, when reacted with HBr/AcOH, did not give the expected 6-bromo-6-deoxy derivative 15, but instead, the 5,6-dibromo-5,6-dideoxy derivative 16 is obtained, that gave a number of condensation products 17-20. Similarly, D-erythro-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone) 21 reacted with thiosemicarbazide furnishing the 2-(phenylhydrazone)-3-thiosemicarbazone 22 characterized by its acetate 23 and rearranged to a pyrazole derivatives 24 and 25.

Keywords : Arylhyaazones, dehydro-L-ascorbic acid, D-arabino-2,3-diulosono-1,4-lactone.

Introduction

Our continuous studies have demonstrated the utilization of carbohydrates in the synthesis of different heterocycles including pyrazoles, triazoles, imidazoles and isoxazoles¹⁻⁶. The observation that pyrazole derivatives are biologically⁷⁻⁹ active, specially as insecticides and anti-inflammatory has promoted the extension of our studies to synthesize a new series of this class of compounds in the hope of producing more effective chemotherapeutic agents. Thus, when D-arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone¹⁰ 1 was treated with *p*-chlorophenylhydrazine, it gave the red bishydrazone 2. Acetylation of 2 with acetic anhydride and pyridine afforded the tri-*O*-acetyl derivative 3, whose NMR spectrum showed three singlets of three proton intensity each at δ 1.96, 2.02 and 2.14. Treatment of 2 or 3 with hydrazine hydrate in methanol, followed by acidification afforded the orange 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-(D-arabino-tetrahydroxybutyl)-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-*p*-(chlorophenylhydrazone) 5 charac-

terized also by giving a tetraacetate 6. As with L-threo-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2,3-bisphenylhydrazone, D-arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2,3-bis(*p*-bromophenylhydrazone)¹¹ 4 was oxidized with cupric chloride in ethanol to give the yellow bicyclic 3,6-anhydro derivative 7. Acetylation of 7 with acetic anhydride and pyridine afforded di-*O*-acetyl-3,6-anhydro-2-oxo-3-*p*-bromophenylazo-D-glucoheptono-1,4-lactone-2-(*p*-bromophenylhydrazone) 8 whose NMR spectrum showed two *O*-acetyl group signals at δ 2.08 and 2.10. *p*-Toluenesulfonation of compound 9 gave 7-*O*-*p*-toluenesulfonyl derivative 10. Treatment of D-arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone 1 with acetylphenylhydrazine in acetic acid solution, gave D-arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone) 11. The mass spectrum of 11 showed the molecular ion peak (also the base peak) at *m/z* 294, followed by a peak at *m/z* 276 resulting from elimination of a molecule of water from the side chain and a fragment at *m/z* 204 due to the loss of

13

Scheme 1

the side chain. Treatment of 11 with benzoylhydrazine, gave the 3-benzoylhydrazone-2-(phenylhydrazone) 12. Acetylation of 11 with acetic anhydride and pyridine, caused simultaneous dehydration and formation of an olefinic compound 13, whose NMR spectrum showed two *O*-acetyl group signals at δ 2.06 and 2.16.

On treatment of L-threo-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(*p*-chlorophenylhydrazine) 14 with HBr/AcOH , did not give the monobromodeoxy derivative 15 expected, instead, it gave 5,6-dibromo-5,6-dideoxy-L-threo-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(*p*-chlorophenylhydrazine) 16 as evident on the basis of its elemental analysis, IR and mass spectral data. Compound 16 has no IR absorption for hydroxyl groups, and showed the lactone carbonyl at 1740 cm^{-1} , in addition to a carbonyl absorption at 1680 cm^{-1} due to (C-3). Treatment of 16 with phenyl-, *p*-nitrophenyl- or *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine, afforded the corresponding bishydrazones 17-19. Similarly, treatment of 16 with thiosemicarbazide gave the 3-thiosemicarbazone 20. Furthermore, treatment of D-erythro-2,3-hexo-

diulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone) 21 with thiosemicarbazide, gave the 2-phenylhydrazone-3-thiosemicarbazone 22 characterized as the diacetyl derivative 23. Treatment of 22 with hydrazine hydrate in methanol, afforded 1-thiocarboxamido-3-(D-erythro-glycerol-1-yl)-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-(phenylhydrazone) 24, which upon periodate oxidation gave, 3-carboxaldehyde-1-thiocarboxamido-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-(phenylhydrazone) 25.

Experimental

M.ps. were recorded on a Tottoli (Büchi) apparatus and are not corrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 580 B spectrophotometer and ^1H NMR spectra (CDCl_3) on a Cameca 250 MHz and Joel 500 MHz spectrometers using TMS as an internal standard. Microanalyses were performed in the Microanalytical Unit, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt. Mass spectra were recorded with an LKB model 2091 mass spectrometer and intensi-

Note

Scheme 2

ties are given in parentheses as a percentage of the base peak.

D-Arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2,3-bis(p-chlorophenylhydrazone) (2): A solution of 1 (1 g; 4.9 mmol) in water-ethanol mixture (40 ml) and *p*-chlorophenylhydrazine hydrochloride (1.8 g), sodium acetate (2 g) and AcOH (5 ml) was heated on a steam bath for 2 h and left to cool at room temperature. The precipitate was filtered off, washed with water and EtOH and dried (0.6 g; 27%). It was recrystallized from EtOH as red needles, m.p. 222–223 °C (Found : C, 50.13; H, 4.18; N, 12.54. C₁₉H₁₈Cl₂N₄O₅ calcd. for : C, 50.35; H, 4.01; N, 12.36%); ν_{\max} : 3445 (OH), 3120 (NH), 1730 cm⁻¹ (lactone C=O).

Tri-O-acetyl-D-arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2,3-bis(p-chlorophenylhydrazone) (3): A solution of 2 (0.1 g; 0.22 mmol) in dry pyridine (5 ml) and Ac₂O (5 ml) was kept overnight at room temperature, then poured

onto crushed ice, and the resulting product was filtered off and washed with water and ethanol and dried (60 mg; 50%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as red needles, m.p. 197–198 °C (Found : C, 51.48; H, 4.31; N, 9.32. C₂₅H₂₄Cl₂N₄O₈ calcd. for : C, 51.83; H, 4.17; N, 9.67%); ν_{\max} : 1755 cm⁻¹ (lactone C=O and ester); δ (CDCl₃) : 1.96, 2.02, 2.14 (3H each, 3s, 3×OAc), 4.83 (2H, dq, CH₂) (*J*_{6,7} 5.27, 13.18 Hz), 5.82 (1H, m, H-6), 5.98 (1H, m, H-5), 6.74 (1H, d, H-4) (*J*_{4,5} 4.32 Hz), 7.26–7.77 (8H, m, Ar-H), 10.21 (1H, s, NH), 11.68 (1H, s, NH).

1-p-Chlorophenyl-3-(D-arabino-tetrahydroxybutyl)-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-(p-chlorophenylhydrazone) (5): A solution of 2 (0.4 g; 0.9 mmol) in methanol (30 ml) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (5 ml) for 1 h, then cooled and acidified with acetic acid. The separated solid was filtered off, washed with methanol and ether and dried (0.3 g; 75%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as orange needles, m.p. 260–261 °C (Found : C, 50.74; H,

4.13; N, 12.06. $C_{19}H_{18}Cl_2N_4O_5$ calcd. for : C, 50.35; H, 4.01; N, 12.36%; ν_{max} : 3450 (OH), 3160 (NH), 1680 cm^{-1} (OCN).

1-p-Chlorophenyl-3-(D-arabino-tetracetoxybutyl)-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-(p-chlorophenylhydrazone) (6) : A solution of 5 (0.1 g; 0.22 mmol) in dry pyridine (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) was kept overnight at room temperature. The mixture was poured onto crushed ice, and the separated solid was filtered off, washed with water, ethanol and ether and dried (60 mg; 46%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as orange needles, m.p. 226–227 °C (Found : C, 52.32; H, 4.32; N, 9.34. $C_{27}H_{26}Cl_2N_4O_9$ calcd. for : C, 52.18; H, 4.21; N, 9.17%; ν_{max} : 3180 (NH), 1740 (ester), 1678 cm^{-1} (OCN); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 2.02, 2.03, 2.09, 2.17 (3H each, 4s, 4 × OAc), 4.26 (2H, dq, CH_2) ($J_{3,4}$ 5.35, 15.10 Hz), 5.33 (1H, m, H-3'), 5.89 (1H, m, H-2'), 6.27 (1H, d, H-1') ($J_{1',2'}$, 4.85 Hz), 7.37–7.98 (8H, m, Ar-H); MS (m/z) : 624 (9.2), 623 (9.2), 622 (30.0), 620 (41), 563 (4.0), 562 (11.3), 561 (6.5), 560 (15.4), 460 (15.5), 459 (8.6), 458 (23.6), 416 (28.1), 415 (16.6), 414 (36.1), 400 (13.9), 398 (35.1), 375 (19.1), 372 (12), 139 (20.9), 111 (39.1).

Di-O-acetyl-3,6-anhydro-2-oxo-3-p-bromophenylazo-D-glucoheptono-1,4-lactone-2-(p-bromophenylhydrazone) (8) : A suspension of D-arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2,3-bis(p-bromophenylhydrazone)¹¹ 7 (0.5 g; 0.91 mmol) in a solution of cupric chloride (10%) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 15 min. Hot water (50 ml) was then added and the resulting solid was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried (0.25 g; 50%), then dissolved in pyridine (5 ml) and treated with acetic anhydride. The mixture was poured onto crushed ice, and the separated solid was filtered off, washed with water and ethanol and dried (60 mg; 53%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 166–167 °C (Found : C, 44.65; H, 3.12; N, 8.64. $C_{23}H_{20}Br_2N_4O_7$ calcd. for : C, 44.3; H, 3.2; N, 9.0%; ν_{max} : 1740 (lactone C=O and ester), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ ($CDCl_3$) : 2.08, 2.10 (3H each, 2s, 2 × OAc), 4.34 (2H, dq, CH_2) ($J_{6,7}$ 4.55, 13.0 Hz), 4.52 (1H, m, H-6), 5.37 (1H, m, H-5), 5.42 (1H, d, H-4) ($J_{4,5}$ 2.14 Hz), 7.19–7.86 (8H, m, ArH), 11.95 (1H, s, NH); MS (m/z) : 438 (7.4), 361 (21.4), 302 (8.2), 301 (47.4), 259 (82.5), 266 (13.1), 242 (4.1), 241 (26.0), 2.13 (5.0), 192 (2.9), 191 (26.7), 106 (4.6), 105 (38.2), 95 (5.2), 93 (32.1), 92 (85.7), 77 (100), 65 (30.7).

7-O-p-Toluenesulfonyl-3,6-anhydro-2-oxo-3-phenylazo-D-glucoheptono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone) (10) : To a solution of 3,6-anhydro-2-oxo-3-phenylazo-D-glucoheptono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone)¹¹ (0.1 g; 26 mmol) in pyridine (5 ml) was added p-toluenesulfonyl chloride (0.1 g) and the mixture was kept overnight at room temperature. It was poured onto crushed ice, and the product was filtered off, washed with water, ethanol and dried (80 mg; 57%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 186–187 °C (Found : C, 58.0; H, 4.69; N, 10.77. $C_{26}H_{24}SN_4O_7$ calcd. for : C, 58.21; H, 4.51; N, 10.44%; ν_{max} : 3450 (OH), 3220 (NH), 1725 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O).

D-Arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone) (11) : A solution of compound 1 (1 g; 5 mmol) in water-ethanol mixture (50 ml) was treated with acetyl phenylhydrazine (1 g; 6 mmol) and acetic acid (5 ml) and heated on a steam bath for 1 h, and left to cool at room temperature. The solid was filtered off, washed with water ethanol and ether and dried (0.4 g; 27%). It was crystallized from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 232–233 °C (Found : C, 53.24; H, 4.72; N, 9.24. $C_{13}H_{14}N_2O_6$ calcd. for : C, 53.06; H, 4.8; N, 9.52%; ν_{max} : 3210 (NH), 1735 (lactone C=O), 1680 cm^{-1} (C-3 C=O); MS (m/z) : 294 (100), 276 (78), 263 (52), 204 (32), 127 (27), 118 (12), 105 (47), 92 (21), 77 (17).

D-Arabino-2,3-heptodiulosono-1,4-lactone-3-benzoylhydrazone-2-(phenylhydrazone) (12) : A solution of compound 11 (90.1 g; 0.34 mmol) in ethanol (20 ml) was treated with benzoylhydrazine (0.1 g) and few drops of acetic acid, and the mixture was heated under reflux for 2 h and left to cool at room temperature. The solid was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried (60 mg; 42%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 246–248 °C (Found : C, 58.64; H, 4.52; N, 13.21. $C_{20}H_{20}N_4O_6$ calcd. for : C, 58.25; H, 4.89; N, 13.53%; ν_{max} : 3160 (NH), 1740 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O).

4-(2',3'-Diacetoxypropylidene)-4-hydroxy-2,3-dioxobutano-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone) (13) : Obtained from compound 11 (0.1 g; 0.34 mmol) as described in the synthesis of 5 (60 mg; 49%). It was crystallized from ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 88–89 °C (Found : C, 56.38; H, 4.21; N, 7.93. $C_{17}H_{16}N_2O_7$ calcd. for : C, 56.67; H, 4.47; N, 7.78%; ν_{max} : 3120 (NH), 1770

(lactone C=O), 1740 cm^{-1} (ester); δ (CDCl_3) : 2.06, 2.16 (3H each, 2s, $2 \times \text{OAc}$), 4.28 (2H, dq, CH_2) ($J_{2,3}$ 3.84, 13.2 Hz), 4.42 (1H, m, H-2), 6.52 (1H, d, H-1), ($J_{1,2}$ 5.23 Hz), 7.02–7.86 (5H, m, ArH), 11.2 (1H, s, NH).

5,6-Dibromo-5,6-dideoxy-L-threo-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(*p*-chlorophenylhydrazone) (16) : A solution of L-threo-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(*p*-chlorophenylhydrazone)¹² **14** (1 g; 3.4 mmol) in HBr-AcOH (30 ml) was stirred for 24 h at room temperature, the mixture was poured onto crushed ice, and the solid was filtered off, washed with water, ethanol and dried (1 g; 67%). It was recrystallized from ethanol-chloroform as yellow needles, m.p. 180–181 °C (Found : C, 33.95; H, 2.31; N, 6.5. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{Br}_2\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 34.0; H, 2.14; N, 6.59%); ν_{max} : 3218 (NH), 1725 (lactone C=O), 1680 cm^{-1} (C-3, C=O); λ_{max} (EtOH) : 240, 368 nm (log ϵ 4.39, 4.37); λ_{min} : 216, 298 nm (log ϵ 3.58, 3.32); MS (m/z) : 426, 433 (30), 344, 342 (12), 330, 328 (15), 153 (15), 151 (36), 141 (8), 127 (100), 113 (18), 111 (50).

Mixed bishydrazones 17-20 : A solution of compound **16** (0.04 mol) and phenyl-, *p*-nitrophenyl-, *p*-sulphamylphenylhydrazine or thiosemicarbazide (0.04 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) and containing a few drops of acetic acid was boiled for 1 h on a steam bath. The solid that separated out on cooling was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried. Each product was recrystallized from ethanol in needles.

17 : m.p. 208–210 °C (Found : C, 41.82; H, 3.14; N, 10.66. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{Br}_2\text{ClN}_4\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 42.00; H, 2.94; N, 10.88%); ν_{max} : 3100 (NH), 1725 cm^{-1} (C=O).

18 : m.p. 226–228 °C (Found : C, 38.81; H, 2.34; N, 12.46. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{Br}_2\text{ClN}_5\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 38.63; H, 12.52; N, 12.52%); ν_{max} : 3080 (NH), 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O).

19 : m.p. 212–213 °C (Found : C, 36.60; H, 2.82; N, 11.92. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{Br}_2\text{ClSN}_5\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 36.41; H, 2.71; N, 11.79%); ν_{max} : 3075 (NH), 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O).

20 : m.p. 168–170 °C (Found : C, 31.62; H, 2.18; N, 14.33. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{Br}_2\text{ClSN}_5\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 31.38; H, 2.42; N, 14.08%); ν_{max} : 3120 (NH), 1725 cm^{-1} (C=O).

D-Erythro-2,2-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone)-3-thiosemicarbazone (22) : A solution of D-

erythro-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone)¹³ **21** (1 g; 3.7 mmol) in ethanol (30 ml) was treated with thiosemicarbazide (1 g) and acetic acid (2 ml) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 6 h, concentrated and left to cool. The product was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried (0.5 g; 39%), crystallized from ethanol as red needles, m.p. 227–228 °C (Found : C, 46.6; H, 4.77; N, 20.52. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{SN}_5\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 46.3; H, 4.48; N, 20.77%); ν_{max} : 3450 (OH), 3120 (NH), 1735 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O).

Di-O-acetyl-D-erythro-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone-2-(phenylhydrazone)-3-thiosemicarbazone (23) : Obtained from **22** as mentioned in the synthesis of **13** (50%), m.p. 124–125 °C (Found : C, 48.32; H, 4.36; N, 16.73. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{SN}_5\text{O}_6$ calcd. for : C, 48.45; H, 4.6; N, 16.62%); ν_{max} : 1735 cm^{-1} (lactone C=O and ester).

1-Thiocarboxamido-3-(D-erythro-glycerol-1-yl)-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-(phenylhydrazone) (24) : A suspension of **22** (1 g; 3 mmol) in concentrated ammonium hydroxide solution (30 ml) was heated on a steam bath under reflux for 30 min and the mixture was left to cool. The solid was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried (0.5 g; 50%), and crystallized from ethanol as orange needle, m.p. 160–162 °C (Found : C, 46.71; H, 4.32; N, 20.51. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{15}\text{SN}_5\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 46.29; H, 4.48; N, 20.8%); ν_{max} : 3400 (OH), 1664 cm^{-1} (OCN).

1-Carboxamido-3-formyl-4,5-pyrazolinedione-4-(phenylhydrazone) (25) : A suspension of **24** (1 g; 3 mmol) in water (20 ml) was treated with sodium metaperiodate (2.1 g; 10 mmol) in water (10 ml) and was shaken for 12 h at room temperature. The solid was filtered off, washed with water, ethanol and dried (0.5 g; 62%). It was crystallized from ethanol as orange needles, m.p. 238–239 °C (Found : C, 47.92; H, 3.12; N, 25.7. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{SN}_5\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 48.0; H, 3.3; N, 25.45%); ν_{max} : 3118 (NH), 1700 (CHO), 1680 cm^{-1} (OCN).

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